

1 **DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A NEW ANALYTICAL METHOD**
2 **FOR THE DETERMINATION OF PLASTICIZERS IN BEE POLLEN**

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14 **Abstract**

15 The determination of plasticizers in bee pollen may be important not only to evaluate the
16 contamination of the hive environment, but also to verify the safety for consumers of this
17 food supplement, since to date it has not been studied. Therefore, a new analytical
18 methodology for the determination of nine plasticizers (phthalate esters: di-(2-ethylhexyl)
19 phthalate, dibutyl phthalate, dimethyl phthalate, diethyl phthalate, benzyl butyl phthalate,
20 and di-*n*-octyl phthalate; diphenyl ethers: 4-bromodiphenyl ether and 4-chlorodiphenyl
21 ether; adipate: bis(2-ethylhexyl) adipate) in bee pollen using gas chromatography-mass
22 spectrometry was developed. An efficient sample treatment (modified QuEChERS, quick,
23 easy, cheap, effective, rugged & safe) is proposed (with average analyte recoveries
24 between 77% and 104%) involving extraction with acetonitrile followed by a dispersive
25 solid phase extraction (enhanced matrix removal lipid sorbent). Chromatographic
26 analysis (< 21 min) was performed in an Agilent HP-5MS column under programmed
27 temperature conditions, and analyses were performed in selected ion monitoring mode.
28 The method was validated in terms of selectivity, limits of detection (0.2–17.2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
29 and quantification (0.5–57.5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), linearity, matrix effect, trueness, and precision
30 (relative standard deviation < 15%). Finally, an analysis of thirty samples from different
31 sources (commercial or experimental apiaries) revealed the presence of residues of five
32 plasticizers in all samples. Quantification was possible in several cases, with overall
33 concentrations ranging from 0.056 to 3.152 mg kg^{-1} . This study not only reports for the
34 first time the presence of some plasticizers in bee pollen, but also corroborates the
35 usefulness of bee pollen as bioindicator of environmental contamination.

36

37 **Keywords:** Adipates; Blue applicability grade index; Diphenyl ethers; GC-MS; Phthalate
38 esters; QuEChERS.

39 1. Introduction

40 In recent years, there has been a significant increase in plastic production, reaching
41 approximately 400 million tons annually in 2022 [1]. Nevertheless, despite its usefulness
42 and ubiquity, current patterns of plastic consumption and disposal are contributing to
43 substantial pollution in the environment [2]. One notable contributor to this pollution is
44 the use of additives, commonly known as plasticizers, aimed at enhancing the properties
45 of plastics. However, the use of plasticizers raises health-related concerns, as they can
46 reach numerous matrices, including food consumed by humans [3]. Some examples of
47 these additives are phthalate esters (PAEs), adipates, polychlorinated diphenyl esters
48 (PCDEs) and polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs). PAEs constitute a class of esters
49 derived from phthalic acid and alcohols containing 4–15 carbon atoms that are commonly
50 used as additives in the manufacture of plastics to enhance properties such as flexibility
51 and elasticity of polymers [4]. However, PAEs lack the capacity to form chemical bonds
52 with the polymer structure, and they tend to migrate from plastics to environmental
53 components and foods. Thus, humans can be exposed to PAEs by multiple routes, and it
54 has been demonstrated that prolonged exposure to PAEs through food intake can have
55 detrimental effects on human health such as endocrine disruption and reproductive
56 toxicity [5,6]. Some of the most used PAEs are di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP),
57 which comprises half of the annual production of PAEs, dibutyl phthalate (DBP) and
58 dimethyl phthalate (DMP). Other examples of PAEs include diethyl phthalate (DEP),
59 benzyl butyl phthalate (BBP), or di-*n*-octyl phthalate (DNOP) [7]. Owing to the health
60 risks associated with PAEs exposure, some restrictions have been established on their use
61 in plastic food contact materials, as outlined in the Regulation (EU) No. 10/2011 [8]. This
62 document includes a list of authorized PAEs in food contact materials, and specific
63 migration limits (SMLs) for some of them like DEHP, DBP, and BBP of 1.50, 0.300 and

64 30.0 mg kg⁻¹, respectively. PAEs for which no SML or other restrictions are provided in
65 this list, such as DEP, DMP, and DNOP, have a generic SML of 60.0 mg kg⁻¹. However,
66 recently, the 16th amendment to Regulation EU 10/2011 on plastic materials and articles
67 intended to come into contact with food was published on July 11, 2023, and it modifies
68 the SMLs for DEHP (1.50 to 0.600 mg kg⁻¹), DBP (0.300 to 0.120 mg kg⁻¹) and BBP
69 (30.0 to 6.00 mg kg⁻¹) [9]. Bis(2-ethylhexyl) adipate (DEHA) emerged as a safer
70 alternative to the most common PAE (DEHP) [10]. While DEHA cannot entirely replace
71 DEHP and other PAEs, it serves as a secondary plasticizer together with other plasticizers
72 to improve low temperature flexibility. Notably, DEHA is primarily used in food contact
73 related applications, constituting over 80% of its usage in the United States [11].
74 However, due to potential health risks, a SML of 18.0 mg kg⁻¹ was established [8].
75 Meanwhile, PBDEs and PCDEs are widely used as flame retardants in the production of
76 plastics. They exhibit persistence in various environmental matrices and have the
77 potential to accumulate in organisms through trophic transfer. Indeed, both types of
78 compounds have been already identified in daily food, a noteworthy observation given
79 their associated reproductive toxicity [12,13]. Within the environment, 4-bromodiphenyl
80 ether (4-BDE) stands out as the predominant mono-brominated diphenyl ether, arising
81 from the photodegradation of more complex brominated PBDEs [14]. On the other hand,
82 biotransformation pathways of PCDEs can lead to the formation of 4-chlorodiphenyl
83 ether (4-CDE) [15]. These two diphenyl ethers are not explicitly listed in the first Annex
84 of Regulation (EU) No. 10/2011 [8]. Therefore, a generic SML of 60 mg kg⁻¹ should be
85 applied.

86 This work focuses on the determination of six PAEs (BBP, DBP, DEHP, DEP, DMP,
87 DNOP), one adipate (DEHA), and two diphenyl ethers (4-BDE and 4-CDE) in bee pollen,
88 which is a natural food made by bees from the pollen grains of flowers, along with a small

89 proportion of nectar [16]. Bees explore extensive areas in their pursuit of nectar and
90 pollen, encountering diverse environmental matrices such as air, water, soils, and plants.
91 If these matrices are polluted by PAEs, adipates, or diphenyl ethers, these compounds will
92 ultimately be introduced into the honey bee colony and hive products, like bee pollen.
93 Therefore, the utilization of bee pollen as a bioindicator of environmental contamination
94 has gained attention in recent years [17,18]. Moreover, like any food product, bee pollen
95 could potentially contain plasticizers, since these compounds may migrate from the
96 packaging into this product [19]. Consequently, given the potential for bee pollen to
97 contain traces of plasticizers, it is crucial to develop specific and sensitive analytical
98 methods with low limits of detection (LODs) and quantification (LOQs) for accurately
99 determining them at low concentrations. Moreover, minimizing the contamination of
100 plasticizers due to their widespread presence in the laboratory is necessary in order to
101 ensure the accurate analysis of samples [20].

102 While no studies for the analysis of these plasticizers in bee pollen have specifically been
103 conducted, PAEs and DEHA have been identified in related bee products, such as honey
104 or royal jelly ([21–27]; see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**). In these works, the
105 proposed sample treatments involved a simple solvent extraction (SE), solid phase
106 extraction (SPE), or a dispersive liquid–liquid microextraction (DLLME) followed by gas
107 chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (GC-MS). However, since bee pollen is a
108 different matrix with other physicochemical properties, such as its insolubility in water,
109 alternative extraction methods must be considered. This is precisely one of the objectives
110 and benefits of this work. Furthermore, PAEs have been found in honey bee wax [28].
111 Nevertheless, the analysis was a non-targeted one, and included several other compounds.
112 Thus, a QuEChERS (Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged & Safe) sample preparation
113 procedure was employed, lacking specificity for PAEs. Moreover, there are some studies

114 in which diphenyl ethers have been analyzed in bee pollen [29,30]. However, the
115 compounds under examination in these studies differ from those analyzed in our research
116 (4-BDE and 4-CDE). These studies included many other compounds, and non-targeted
117 approaches were employed. Finally, it is important to note that the most employed
118 analytical technique for determining PAEs, adipates, PBDEs and PCDEs (and their
119 metabolites) in foods is GC-MS [31–35], and regarding sample treatment, the prevailing
120 approach is classical SE [35–39]. However, it should be noted that numerous preparation
121 methods can be used to prepare samples for analysis of these compounds in foods, in
122 addition to classical SE. Methods such as liquid-phase microextraction, accelerated
123 solvent extraction, stir-bar sorptive extraction, SPE, and column chromatographic
124 cleanup have been employed in several publications. However, these methods are
125 expensive, insensitive, and time-consuming [40,41]. Therefore, it is not surprising that
126 alternative methods that do not present the aforementioned disadvantages, such as the
127 previously-mentioned QuEChERS [28,42-45], and magnetic solid phase extraction
128 (MSPE) with different particles, such as multi-walled carbon nanotubes magnetized with
129 iron, have been recently used to determine plasticizers in foods [41,42,46,47]. For
130 example, compared to the traditional SPE procedure, MSPE methods present some
131 advantages, including increased effectiveness, time savings, and a less labour-intensive
132 approach [47].

133 Therefore, the main objective of this study is to introduce a method for the simultaneous
134 determination of nine plasticizers in bee pollen using GC-MS. It is worth noting that, to
135 the best of our knowledge, no studies have proposed an analytical methodology for the
136 detection of all those mentioned compounds in bee pollen, either simultaneously or
137 individually. Thus, this marks the first attempt to monitor these compounds in bee pollen.
138 Another objective of this work is to propose an efficient, simple, cheap, and fast sample

139 treatment applicable. We aim to minimize time, cost, steps, and reagent usage, addressing
140 some of the limitations found in previous studies. Our study also intends to validate the
141 proposed method and analyze experimental and commercial bee pollen samples from
142 different origins (botanical and geographical).

143

144 **2. Material and methods**

145 2.1. Reagents and materials

146 PAEs, adipate and diphenyl ethers standards (BBP, DBP, dibutyl phthalate-3,4,5,6-d₄ –
147 DBP-d₄, DEHP, DEP, DMP, DNOP, DEHA, 4-BDE and 4-CDE; see structures in
148 Supplementary Material, **Figure 1S**), all of analytical-grade and with purity greater than
149 98%, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie Gbmh (Steinheim, Germany). It is
150 important to note that two separate standard mixtures were obtained: one containing the
151 six PAEs and DEHA (EPA-506), and another consisting of the six PAEs in addition to 4-
152 BDE and 4-CDE (EPA-8270). All solvents and reagents were of
153 chromatographic/analytical grade. Acetonitrile and methanol were obtained from VWR
154 Prolabo Chemicals (Fontenay-sous-Bois, France), acetone and ethyl acetate were
155 supplied by Carlo Erba Reagents-SA (Milan, Italy), nitric acid was provided by ITW
156 Reagents (Monza, Italy), 1,2-propanediol was purchased from Montplet & Esteban S.A.
157 (Barcelona, Spain), and heptane, methyl tert-butyl ether, and choline chloride were from
158 Sigma-Aldrich Chemie Gbmh. Ultrapure water was obtained using Millipore Milli-RO
159 plus and Milli-Q systems (Bedford, MA, USA). A vortex mechanical mixer from
160 Heidolph (Schwabach, Germany), a thermostated ultrasound bath, a drying oven, all
161 supplied by J.P. Selecta S.A. (Barcelona, Spain), a 5810 R refrigerated bench-top
162 centrifuge from Eppendorf (Hamburg, Germany), a Moulinette chopper device from

163 Moulinex (Paris, France), and PTFE syringe filters (17 mm, 0.2 μm ; Branchia, Labbox,
164 Spain) were employed for sample treatment. QuEChERS dispersive solid phase
165 extraction (dSPE) enhanced matrix removal lipid (EMR-Lipid) sorbent was supplied by
166 Agilent Technologies (Folsom, CA, USA), while C_{18} was provided by Supelco
167 (Bellefonte, PA, USA), and Florisil was provided by Alltech Associates, Inc. (Deerfield,
168 IL, USA).

169 It should be noted that, owing to the common presence of PAEs in the laboratory
170 environment, it is crucial to control their potential presence in the background signal
171 values of blanks [20]. To address this issue, plastic consumables (micropipettes tips) and
172 chemical reagents were newly used/opened, and the absence of any residues of PAEs was
173 verified. Moreover, laboratory glassware underwent a meticulous cleaning process with
174 ultrapure water, nitric acid, and ultrapure water again, followed by a final wash with a
175 mixture of acetone and methanol (1:1, v/v) before being dried in an oven at approximately
176 150°C for 60 minutes. Procedural blanks, in which ultrapure water replaced bee pollen,
177 were systematically run between sets of samples to monitor potential abnormal
178 background values. BBP was detected with constant response in all the procedural blanks,
179 and consequently, the blank response of this compound was systematically subtracted in
180 every analysis.

181

182 2.2. Preparation of standard solutions

183 Standard stock solutions (at a concentration of 1000.0 mg L^{-1}) and working solutions for
184 the analyzed compounds were prepared using acetone. It is important to note that two
185 separate stock solutions were prepared according to the obtained standard mixtures (six
186 PAEs and DEHA, EPA-506; six PAEs, 4-BDE and 4-CDE; EPA-8270). Bee pollen
187 samples were spiked with variable amounts of the analytes either before (BF samples) or

188 after (AF samples) sample treatment (see **section 2.3**) to prepare the standard in matrix
189 extracts. The spiking of the samples was done similarly to Fuente-Ballesteros et al. [48].
190 Representative portions of ground and dried bee pollen were weighed and transferred to
191 a crystallizer. Subsequently, these portions were uniformly spiked with the working
192 solutions. Meanwhile, AF samples were prepared by spiking previously treated bee pollen
193 samples (subjected to the proposed sample treatment) with working standard solutions,
194 which were added to the reconstitution solvent. The internal standard (IS; DBP-d₄) was
195 consistently added at the same concentration (0.100 mg L⁻¹). It should be mentioned that
196 the IS was not added from the beginning of the sample treatment but at the reconstitution
197 stage in the final method, as the studied compounds were extracted in all cases with
198 enough efficiency and precision (see **subsection 3.3.6**), and what was intended to
199 compensate was the variability in the intensity of the MS signals due to differences in
200 ionization efficiency. These samples were used for validation (spiked samples (low,
201 medium, and high) and calibration curves), as well as sample treatment studies. The study
202 involved the preparation of three replicates, each of which was injected three times. Each
203 spiked sample was prepared with a blank sample fortified with three different
204 concentrations of the plasticizers within the linear range. These were as follows: low-
205 LOQ (see **Table 1**); medium-0.400 mg kg⁻¹; high-2.000 mg kg⁻¹. The standard stock
206 solutions were stored in glass containers in darkness at -20 °C, and working and standard
207 matrix solutions were stored in glass containers and kept in the dark at 4 °C until the
208 analysis.

209

210 2.3. Sample procurement and treatment

211 2.3.1. Samples

212 A total of thirty bee pollen samples ($n = 30$, see **Table 2S**) were divided into two groups:
213 those obtained from experimental apiaries ($n = 15$; E1-E15), which were kindly donated
214 by researchers from the Center for Agroenvironmental and Apicultural Investigation
215 (CIAPA, Marchamalo, Guadalajara, Spain); and those of commercial origin ($n = 15$; C1-
216 C15), which were purchased from local markets in Spain. The botanical origin of the bee
217 pollen samples was confirmed by palynological analysis at CIAPA [49]. All the samples
218 were dried at 45 °C in an oven, individually ground in a mill, and subsequently stored in
219 a vacuum desiccator before analysis [48]. Three replicates (sub-samples) of each bee
220 pollen sample, injected in triplicate, were examined to determine the plasticizers content.

221 2.3.2. Sample treatment

222 An efficient sample treatment based on the QuEChERS methodology [50] has been used,
223 but it has been adapted and refined in this study to specifically determine plasticizers in
224 bee pollen. Briefly, 1.000 g of dried and ground bee pollen was weighed in a 10 mL glass
225 centrifuge tube, and 4.00 mL of acetonitrile was added. Then, the tube was then shaken
226 at 1400 rpm for 1 min in a vortex device and placed in an ultrasound bath for 10 min.
227 After that, the mixture was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 5 min at 5°C, and the resulting
228 supernatant was collected. Subsequently, 1.000 g of EMR Lipid was added, and the entire
229 process (vortex, ultrasonication, centrifugation) was repeated. Afterward, 1.00 mL of the
230 supernatant was collected and evaporated to dryness under a nitrogen stream at room
231 temperature (≈ 10 min). Finally, the dry extract was reconstituted with 1.00 mL of an IS
232 solution (0.100 mg L^{-1}) in acetone and filtered through a $0.2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ PTFE filter prior GC-
233 MS analysis. **Figure 2S** (see Supplementary Material) summarizes the steps of the
234 selected sample treatment.

235

236 2.4. GC-MS conditions

237 An Agilent Technologies (Palo Alto, CA, USA) 7890A gas chromatograph (GC) coupled
238 to an Agilent Technologies 5975C mass spectrometer (MS) equipped with an ALS 7693B
239 autosampler and a MS ChemStation E 01.00.237 software (Agilent Technologies) was
240 employed. The chromatographic column was an Agilent HP-5MS (30 m × 250 μm × 0.25
241 μm). The GC-MS parameters (programmed temperature conditions; temperatures
242 (injector, transfer line, ion source, and quadrupole), flow rate, injection mode and volume,
243 etc.), which were optimized in a previous and recent work [27], are summarized in **Table**
244 **2**. It should be mentioned that after determining each analyte's retention time via full-scan
245 mode, optimization of SIM mode was conducted to guarantee precise identification and
246 high signal intensity for each analyte. A full scan of the standard solution for each
247 plasticizer was done to obtain its mass spectrum and compare it with the NIST mass
248 spectra library. Molecular ions, highly abundant fragment ions, and distinctive ions were
249 chosen and adjusted to minimize interference and facilitate accurate analyte qualification
250 and quantification. Based on these criteria, specific ions were selected for quantification,
251 while two additional ions were chosen for qualitative evaluation for each plasticizer (see
252 **Table 2**). Under these optimal GC-MS conditions, all compounds eluted in < 21 min (see
253 **Figure 1**). As can be seen, the compounds can be identified/quantified without problems
254 using the ions selected for each of them, even though they would not be separated to the
255 baseline. This fact highlights one of the advantages of using MS detectors: their ability to
256 discriminate between co-eluting compounds by employing different ions for each.

257

258 3. Results and discussion

259 3.1. Optimization of the sample treatment

260 As most of the analytes studied are PAEs, the optimization of the sample treatment was
261 initially focused on them, and the optimization process of the sample treatment started
262 six PAEs (BBP, DBP, DEHP, DEP, DMP, and DNOP) and two diphenyl ethers (4-BDE
263 and 4-CDE). It should be remarked that the first experiments were conducted with a
264 spiking concentration of 0.250 mg L^{-1} (1.000 mg kg^{-1}), and that the optimization process
265 considered the percentages of recovery (%R) and matrix effect (%ME) of the analytes.

266 In our effort to develop a sample treatment in line with the principles of green analytical
267 chemistry, an attempt was made to employ natural deep eutectic solvents (NADES).
268 NADES consist of two or more components in solid or liquid states, serving as a hydrogen
269 bond acceptor and a hydrogen bond donor, combined in a specific molar ratio. The
270 preparation process involves the physical mixing of these components under heating and
271 vigorous stirring [51]. Following a recently reported synthesis of NADES for the
272 extraction of PAEs and DEHA, which employed a mixture of choline chloride and 1,2-
273 propanediol [52], two tests were conducted. In the first test, 1.000 g of bee pollen was
274 weighed, and 4 mL of NADES were added, initiating a SE using vortex (1400 rpm, 1
275 min), ultrasonication (10 min), and centrifugation (4000 rpm, 5 min, 5°C). Subsequently,
276 the supernatant underwent sequential SE with an ethyl acetate and heptane (1:1, v/v)
277 mixture. After applying vortexing, ultrasonication, and centrifugation under the same
278 conditions mentioned earlier, the organic phase was evaporated under nitrogen stream at
279 room temperature. Finally, the dry extract was reconstituted with 1.00 mL of acetone. In
280 the second test, 2.00 mL of ultrapure water and 3.00 mL of NADES were added to the
281 bee pollen sample, and the same extraction process was repeated, using only ethyl acetate
282 in the SE step. Unfortunately, both tests resulted in low recoveries ($< 30 \%$), leading to

283 the decision to discard the use of NADES in our sample treatment. One possible reason
284 that could explain the poor results obtained using NADES is the nature of the matrix
285 under study, since bee pollen is very different from the matrices analyzed in previous
286 studies (tropical fruits [51]; laying hen and goat feed [52]).

287 Given that PAEs from foods are typically extracted through SE, our next approach
288 consisted of weighing 1.000 g of bee pollen, followed by a SE by using 4 mL of different
289 solvents: ethyl acetate, ethyl acetate and heptane (1:1, v/v) mixture, acetonitrile, and
290 methyl tert-butyl ether. These solvents were chosen because they provided promising
291 results in previous analyses conducted by the research group when these compounds were
292 analyzed in honey [27]. The sample underwent a sequential process involving vortex
293 mixing (1400 rpm, 1 min), ultrasonication (10 min), centrifugation (4000 rpm, 5 min,
294 5°C), evaporation of the organic phase under an N₂ stream, and reconstitution of the dry
295 residue with acetone. The best results in terms of recovery were achieved with acetonitrile
296 (data not shown). However, despite acceptable recoveries (96%–125%), elevated ME
297 were observed (experiment T1; > 200% in some cases; see Supplementary Material,
298 **Table 3S**). Therefore, a test involving the addition of sorbents for a clean-up step
299 (dispersive solid-phase extraction, dSPE) was conducted to address the high ME. Three
300 approaches were employed: one with EMR Lipid alone (see Supplementary Material,
301 **Table 3S**; experiment T2), another with both EMR Lipid and C₁₈ (see Supplementary
302 Material, **Table 3S**; experiment T3), and a third with both EMR Lipid and Florisil together
303 (see Supplementary Material, **Table 3S**; Experiment T4). In all these tests, 1.000 g of each
304 sorbent was used. The results indicated that, while the ME was not entirely corrected for
305 most compounds, there was a substantial improvement due to the clean-up step (< 400%
306 in all cases). In view of the results of the application of three sorbents, the use of Florisil
307 was excluded from further consideration, and experiments T2 and T3 were replicated at

308 a higher concentration (0.500 mg L⁻¹ or 2.000 mg kg⁻¹; see Supplementary Material, **Table**
309 **3S**; experiments T5 and T6, respectively). At this high level of concentration, the results
310 obtained were better for the addition of EMR Lipid alone (experiment T5; %R between
311 79% and 96%). Consequently, the suitability of the extraction with 4.00 mL of acetonitrile
312 and the clean-up step with the addition of EMR Lipid (1.000 g) was checked at three
313 concentration levels (see **section 2.2**). It is important to note that DEHA had not been
314 included up to this point; however, it was at this stage, with three replicates conducted for
315 each concentration level. Although the presence of ME is evident (> ±20% in most cases),
316 the sample treatment provides acceptable recoveries (77% – 104%) for all the analytes at
317 the three concentration levels (see Supplementary Material, **Table 4S**). Moreover, tests
318 were carried out with different amounts of bee pollen (0.500-1.500 g), larger volumes of
319 acetonitrile (6.00 and 8.00 mL), extended extraction times (15 min), and increased
320 amounts of sorbent (1.500 g). However, these adjustments did not improve the previous
321 ones (data not shown). It should be mentioned that the observed differences in the
322 influence of the ME on the signal of the compounds may be tentatively explained by the
323 different structures of the plasticizers, since they belong to three different groups of
324 compounds. Alternatively, the ME might be because plasticizers are affected by different
325 bee pollen components that could coelute with them without being observed and without
326 affecting their chromatographic separation when working in SIM mode [27]. However,
327 considering that the matrix effect can be effectively addressed by incorporating standard
328 in matrix calibration curves for quantification, and given the good recoveries, the
329 conditions detailed above and summarized in **subsection 2.3.2** were considered
330 definitive.

331 To sum up, the proposed sample treatment can be considered as a good option to
332 determine plasticizers in bee pollen as it is relatively fast (≈ 35 min), simple (few stages

333 and with common instrumentation), involves little use of reagents (solvents, 5.00 mL;
334 sorbents, 1.000 g), and it can be considered economical. Moreover, recovery values were
335 satisfactory for all the analytes studied, and, although the matrix effect was significant for
336 most compounds, this can be compensated by using matrix-matched calibration curves
337 for quantification. When comparing the proposed sample treatment with previous ones
338 dedicated to analyzing plasticizers in other products from the hive, or those that use
339 QuEChERS-based methods in other foods (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**), it can
340 be concluded that the performance is very similar. It is worth noting that some similar
341 works analyzing plasticizers in bee products [26,28-30] were omitted from **Table 1S** (see
342 Supplementary Material) because non-targeted analyses were conducted, and/or
343 recoveries, limits of detection (LODs) and limits of quantification (LOQs) were not
344 calculated. The recovery percentages were between 70% and 120% in all cases, and
345 plasticizers were usually quantified with matrix-matched calibration curves with only two
346 exceptions [23,28]. The treatment time and the number of stages required are very similar
347 in most cases, being slightly lower in those methodologies based on DLLME [21,22,24].
348 These methods also use fewer solvents and reagents, compared to QuEChERS-based
349 methodologies [27,42-45], including the proposed method. In contrast, the most classic
350 methodologies (SE [23]; SPE [25]) are the most time-consuming and require the greatest
351 consumption of solvents. However, it should be emphasized that the primary distinction
352 and significant novelty/relevance in this work lies in the fact that it is the first time that a
353 specific sample treatment has been proposed to determine these compounds in bee pollen.
354 Furthermore, the performance of the proposed sample treatment is comparable to those
355 previously published in very different matrices, which demonstrates its effectiveness and
356 usefulness.

357

358 3.2. Method validation

359 Validation was performed according to current legislation [53]. In addition, several of the
360 main elements of uncertainty [54] were considered when optimizing and validating this
361 method (amount of sample used, recovery value of the analytical procedure, precision,
362 and repeatability). The specific procedures for determining the different validation
363 parameters are summarized in **Table 5S**.

364 *3.2.1. Selectivity*

365 Selectivity was evaluated by comparing the chromatograms and mass spectra of standards
366 in solvents with blanks of bee pollen. No matrix interferences were detected at the
367 retention times of the analytes, except for BBP, which is also present in procedural blanks
368 (data not shown). Additionally, comparable mass spectra were obtained for the standards
369 of plasticizers in both solvents and matrix extracts (see **Figure 2**), although certain minor
370 differences in ion intensity were observed and certain low intensity ions appeared only in
371 bee pollen spectra.

372 *3.2.2. Limits of detection and quantification*

373 LODs and LOQs are summarized in **Table 1**. They ranged from 0.2 to 17.2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ and
374 from 0.5 to 57.5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, respectively. Those values are below to the SMLs established
375 by legislation [8,9], and they are similar or even better than those obtained in previous
376 works in other matrices with similar compounds (LODs, 0.01-600 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; LOQs, 0.04-
377 1500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**). These results demonstrate the
378 excellent sensitivity of the proposed method.

379 *3.2.3. Matrix effect*

380 To ascertain how the matrix influenced ESI ionization for the compounds, a comparison
381 was made by analyzing the detector responses (analyte peak area/IS area) of standards in

382 solvent and AF samples spiked at three different concentrations. The results showed that
383 there is significant ME in most cases (see Supplementary Material, **Table 4S**).
384 Nevertheless, this ME can be addressed by using matrix-matched calibration curves for
385 the quantification, as it has been done in most related works (see Supplementary Material,
386 **Table 1S**). The ME was not significant in only two cases, which involved matrices quite
387 different from bee pollen (mussels [42], honey and royal jelly [23]).

388 *3.2.4. Linearity/Working range*

389 Matrix-matched calibration curves (BF samples) were used to quantify the analytes in bee
390 pollen samples due to the significant ME. Calibration curves ($n = 6$) were constructed by
391 plotting the signal on the y-axis (analyte peak area/IS area) against analyte concentration
392 on the x-axis. Concentration of the analytical curves varied between LOQ, and 0.500 mg
393 L⁻¹ (LOQ, 0.025, 0.050, 0.075, 0.100, 0.250 and 0.500 mg L⁻¹), which corresponds to
394 those between LOQ and 2.000 mg kg⁻¹. It should be mentioned that the Breusch-Pagan
395 test [55] was performed to build the calibration model, and the results confirmed that
396 homoscedasticity and independency of residuals are met in all cases (data not shown).
397 Moreover, the graphs obtained in all the calibration curves were straight lines, with the
398 coefficient of the determination values (R^2) higher than 0.99 in all cases (see **Table 1**),
399 and the deviation of back-calculation concentration from true concentration was lower
400 than 20% (data not shown).

401 *3.2.5. Precision*

402 Precision is expressed as the relative standard deviation (%RSD). This was measured
403 through repeated sample analyses using BF samples spiked at three different
404 concentration levels (see **section 2.2**). These experiments took place either on the same
405 day (repeatability), or over three consecutive days (partial reproducibility). %RSD values
406 were consistently lower than 15% in all cases (see Supplementary Material, **Table 6S**),

407 which fits perfectly with the values reported in previous works (<20%; see Supplementary
408 Material, **Table 1S**).

409 3.2.6. *Trueness*

410 Trueness was evaluated through recovery experiments by comparing the results (analyte
411 peak area/IS area) between BF samples and AF samples, which were obtained from blank
412 samples spiked at three different concentrations (see **section 2.2**). Mean recoveries for the
413 analytes studied ranged in all cases from 77% to 104% (**Table 4S**), with %RSD values
414 lower than 15% (data not shown). These results are again comparable to those obtained
415 in the related works included in **Table 1S** (70%-120%; see Supplementary Material).

416

417 3.3. Assessment of the applicability of the method

418 The blue applicability grade index (BAGI) was applied to evaluate the practicality and
419 applicability of the employed analytical methodology [56]. BAGI is a novel and simple
420 to use index that can efficiently assess the applicability of an analytical method. BAGI is
421 complementary to the green assessment tools, and it revolves around the “blue” principles
422 of White Analytical Chemistry, which are mainly related to practical aspects. BAGI
423 considers ten main attributes, such as the type of analysis, the number of analytes that are
424 simultaneously determined, the required instrumentation, or the automation degree, to
425 produce a pictogram and a score that depicts the applicability of an analytical method in
426 terms of practicality. A sequential blue colour scale is used to represent the final score,
427 with colors like dark blue, blue, light blue, and white, which represent high, medium, low,
428 and no compliance with the method's practical criteria, respectively. Moreover, according
429 to BAGI guidelines, a total score exceeding 60.0 is recommended for an analytical
430 method to be considered practical [56]. Therefore, to calculate the BAGI of the proposed

431 method, its main attributes must be considered. The method involved a quantitative,
432 confirmatory, and multi-element analysis of nine plasticizers by GC-MS, with a
433 modified-QuEChERS extraction allowing for complete analysis of 2-4 samples per hour.
434 In addition, common and commercially available reagents were used. The method
435 involved minimal sample (1.000 g of bee pollen per sample), a preconcentration step, and
436 semi-automated analysis using a GC autosampler. Taking all these factors into account,
437 the method achieved a score of 65.0 (see **Figure 3**), surpassing the 60-point threshold,
438 which demonstrates its applicability. When comparing the value obtained with the
439 proposed method to those reported in the studies collected in **Table 1S** (see
440 Supplementary Material), it is evident that the applicability score (BAGI) is comparable
441 with most works. Specifically, the value obtained in the proposed method is equal to or
442 greater than that of previous works, except for two cases (75.0-DLLME [24]; 70.0-
443 QuEChERS [43]). However, it must be highlighted again that this comparison is
444 approximate, since neither the matrices nor the compounds analyzed are the same, which
445 have a great influence when developing the methods.

446

447 3.4. Application of the method

448 The validated method was applied for determining potential analyte residues in thirty bee
449 pollen samples (see **subsection 2.3.1**). IS was added to all samples at the same
450 concentration (0.100 mg L⁻¹ or 0.400 mg kg⁻¹). Moreover, sample E10 was diluted (1:2)
451 for the quantification. The results are detailed in **Table 7S** (see Supplementary Material).
452 Four compounds, two PAEs (DMP and DNOP) and the two diphenyl ethers (4-CDE and
453 4-BDE) were not detected in any of the samples. In contrast, DBP and DEHA were
454 detected in all samples, while DEP, BBP and DEHP were found in only some of them.
455 DEHA was found to be the only analyte quantified in all samples, followed closely by

456 DBP. Notably, DBP was quantified in every sample from experimental apiaries and nearly
457 all commercial samples, except for one. Despite not being quantified in every sample,
458 BBP exhibited the highest concentrations overall, and in one sample (E10), the
459 concentration value was 2.414 mg kg⁻¹. In contrast, among the quantified analytes, DEHP
460 was found in the lowest concentrations (< 0.180 mg kg⁻¹). It should be highlighted that
461 the overall concentrations ranged from 0.056 to 3.152 mg kg⁻¹ (see Supplementary
462 Material, **Table 7S**). Upon comparing commercial samples to those from experimental
463 apiaries, it was observed that a greater number of analytes were both detected and
464 quantified in the experimental samples. The observed disparity can be tentatively
465 explained from the processing methods applied to commercial bee pollen. Fresh bee
466 pollen, containing between 20% and 30% water, requires a drying process. However, this
467 drying procedure, which can involve elevated temperatures [57], may lead to a potential
468 partial loss of analytes due to their low boiling points. It is noteworthy that this processing
469 step is not conducted in samples from experimental apiaries. Additionally, residues have
470 been detected in bee pollen from both plastic and glass containers, although most of the
471 containers were glass, which accounts for the higher number of positive findings in this
472 material. Despite this, there is considerable variability in residue concentrations across
473 different containers, with the highest concentrations generally found in glass. However,
474 no clear correlation between container material and residue levels has been established.
475 Regarding the floral origin of the samples, no significant conclusions can be drawn, as
476 most samples are of multifloral origin and the number of samples from other floral
477 sources is insufficient. Future studies should aim to increase the sample size and include
478 bee pollen from various geographical and botanical origins, as well as a broader range of
479 packaging types, to gain a more comprehensive understanding. However, it is important
480 to note that all the analytes in bee pollen samples were found to be significantly below

481 the established SMLs ([8,9]; see **Table 1** and **Table 7S**). This regulatory compliance
482 ensures that there is no discernible risk associated with the consumption of these bee
483 pollen samples in relation to their content of plasticizers.

484 The occurrence of plasticizer residues, particularly PAEs and adipates, in bee pollen is a
485 novel finding, since to our knowledge, this is the first time that the presence of these
486 compounds has been detected/investigated in this bee product. However, residues of these
487 compounds have been detected in other bee matrices, especially honey (see
488 Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**). In the case of honey, variable amounts of these
489 compounds have been found, ranging from 0.001 mg kg⁻¹ [23] to more than 5.000 mg kg⁻¹
490 [22], and the compounds found in the highest concentration and number of samples were
491 DHP, DEP, DEHA and BBP [21-25,27]. These findings are somewhat consistent with the
492 results obtained in the present study, since the presence of plasticizers in honey may
493 originate from contaminated pollen and nectar [22,27]. When comparing to other food
494 matrices such as those mentioned in **Table 1S** (mussels, oil, baby food, and capsanthin;
495 see Supplementary Material), a similar trend is observed. The plasticizers DEHP, DEP
496 and BBP are the most frequently detected and are found at the highest concentrations,
497 with variability comparable to that seen in honey (0.001 mg kg⁻¹ [45] to 4.930 mg kg⁻¹
498 [44]).

499 Finally, the identification of contaminant residues associated with plastics in bee pollen
500 underscores the importance of developing analytical methods to ensure the safety of this
501 bee product and preserve human health, since some of them had been classified as
502 endocrine disruptors [22,23,27]. While this issue has been widely studied in different
503 types of food, beverages and food stimulants [35], there is no information regarding bee
504 pollen samples. Moreover, in accordance with the European Regulation, the limitation of
505 60 mg kg⁻¹ for those compounds without a defined SML requires careful consideration.

506

507 **4. Conclusions**

508 This study introduces a new analytical method combining a modified QuEChERS with
509 GC-MS, that has been successfully developed and validated for the determination of six
510 PAEs, one adipate, and two diphenyl ethers in bee pollen. The method is efficient, simple,
511 fast, and economical, involving SE with acetonitrile and a further dSPE with a EMR-lipid
512 sorbent. With this procedure, good recovery percentages have been achieved for all the
513 compounds, but the matrix effect could not be minimized enough. In addition, the GC-
514 MS method has been specifically developed for this study, and under the proposed
515 conditions, all analytes were eluted in less than 21 minutes. The proposed method has
516 been validated, and the results showed that the analytical performance of the method was
517 good enough and comparable with related studies. The LODs and LOQs were
518 significantly lower than the established SMLs, and similar or even better than previous
519 works. Therefore, the initial hypothesis presented in the Introduction, underscoring the
520 necessity for selective and sensitive methods in discerning plasticizers in bee pollen, was
521 achieved. The application of this method to thirty samples revealed that five out of the
522 nine analytes were detected, each exhibiting concentration well below the SML. It is
523 important to note that differences were observed between samples of commercial origin
524 and those from experimental apiaries. On the other hand, a relationship between
525 plasticizer content and floral origin or container material could not be established due to
526 the limited diversity of the samples, as most were multifloral and collected in glass
527 containers. Future studies should therefore include a larger and more diverse sample set,
528 analyzing bee pollen with various floral origins and packaging materials using the
529 proposed method. This would allow for a more comprehensive assessment and enable

530 more meaningful conclusions about the potential influences of floral origin and container
531 material on plasticizer content. Lastly, this study represents a significant milestone as the
532 first-ever analytical method for the determination of PAEs, diphenyl ethers, and adipates
533 in bee pollen, either individually (PAEs and diphenyl ethers) or simultaneously (all
534 compounds). Therefore, it serves as the first attempt to systematically monitor these
535 compounds in bee pollen, providing valuable insights to the field.

536

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544

545 **Conflict of interest statement**

546 The authors of this manuscript declare no conflict of interest.

547

548 **Data availability**

549 The datasets generated during the current study are included in this published article, or
550 they are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

551

552 **List of abbreviations**

553 **AF**, samples spiked after sample treatment; **BF**, samples spiked before sample treatment;
554 **4-BDE**, 4-bromodiphenyl ether; **4-CDE**, 4-chlorodiphenyl ether; **BBP**, butyl benzyl
555 phthalate; **CIAPA**, center for agroenvironmental and apicultural investigation; **DBP**,
556 dibutyl phthalate; **DBP-d₄**, dibutyl phthalate-3,4,5,6-d₄ **DEHA**, bis(2-ethylhexyl)
557 adipate; **DEHP**, di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; **DEP**, diethyl phthalate; **DLLME**, dispersive
558 liquid–liquid microextraction; **DMP**, dimethyl phthalate; **DNOP**, di-*n*-octyl phthalate;
559 **dSPE**, dispersive solid-phase extraction; **GC-MS**, gas chromatography coupled to mass
560 spectrometry; **IS**, internal standard; **LOD**, limit of detection; **LOQ**, limit of
561 quantification; **ME**, matrix effect; **MSPE**, magnetic solid-phase extraction; **NADES**,
562 natural deep eutectic solvents; **PAEs**, phthalate esters; **PBDEs**, polybrominated diphenyl
563 ethers; **PCDEs**, polychlorinated diphenyl ethers; **QuEChERS**, quick, easy, cheap,
564 effective, rugged & safe; **%R**, recovery percentage; **R²**: coefficient of the determination;
565 **%RSD**, relative standard deviation; **SE**, solvent extraction; **SIM**, selected ion
566 monitoring; **SML**, specific migration limit; **SPE**, solid-phase extraction.

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793 **Figure captions**

794 **Figure 1.-** Representative Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry (GC-MS) chromatograms
795 (selected ion monitoring mode using the quantification/target ions; see **Table 2**) obtained from
796 standards in solvent mixture (0.5 mg L⁻¹; IS, 0.1 mg L⁻¹). GC-MS conditions are summarized
797 in **section 2.4** and **Table 2**. **1**, dimethyl phthalate (DMP); **2**, diethyl phthalate (DEP); **3**, 4-
798 chlorodiphenyl ether (4-CDE); **4**, 4-bromodiphenyl ether (4-BDE); **5**, dibutyl phthalate (DBP);
799 **6**, dibutyl phthalate-3,4,5,6-d4 (DBP-d4; internal standard); **7**, butyl benzyl phthalate (BBP); **8**,
800 bis(2-ethylhexyl) adipate (DEHA), **9**, di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP); **10**, di-n-octyl
801 phthalate (DNOP).

802 **Figure 2.-** Mass spectra of dibutyl phthalate (DBP) in (A) standard in solvent, (B) spiked bee
803 pollen sample. Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry conditions are summarized in **section**
804 **2.4** and **Table 2**.

805 **Figure 3.-** Blue applicability grade index (BAGI) index pictogram of the proposed analytical
806 method.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Table 1.- Calibration curve data (matrix-matched standards SCI, slope confidence interval; ICI, intercept confidence interval), limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ), and specific migration limits (SMLs).

Analyte	SCI	ICI	R ²	LOD ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	SML (mg kg^{-1} ; [8,9])
DMP	0.00499 \pm 0.00047	0.06134 \pm 0.10976	0.995	1.0	3.3	60
DEP	0.00450 \pm 0.00037	0.16446 \pm 0.45661	0.997	0.3	0.9	60
4-CDE	0.00162 \pm 0.00016	0.02837 \pm 0.09028	0.997	0.7	2.5	60
4-BDE	0.00164 \pm 0.00015	0.02036 \pm 0.06479	0.997	0.2	0.8	60
DBP	0.00711 \pm 0.00053	0.10033 \pm 0.27855	0.997	1.3	4.4	0.12
BBP	0.00398 \pm 0.00063	0.17570 \pm 0.18033	0.993	0.5	1.7	6
DEHA	0.00566 \pm 0.00178	-0.09474 \pm 0.50673	0.990	0.2	0.5	18
DEHP	0.00896 \pm 0.00045	0.11776 \pm 0.10507	0.999	2.9	9.7	0.6
DNOP	0.00402 \pm 0.00032	0.03786 \pm 0.07544	0.997	17.2	57.5	60

Table 2.- GC-MS parameters.

GC parameter	Final setting
Programmed temperature conditions	From 60 °C (1 min) to 125 °C at 25 °C min ⁻¹ , then increased to 310 °C at 10 °C min ⁻¹ , and finally kept for 3 min at 310 °C.
Carrier gas	Helium
Transfer line temperature (°C)	310
Injection mode	Splitless
Flow rate (mL/min)	1.2
Injector temperature (°C)	280
Injection volume (μL)	1

MS parameter	Final setting
Operating mode	Electron impact
Ionization energy (eV)	70
Scan range (<i>m/z</i>)	25-300
Ion source temperature (°C)	230
Quadrupole temperature (°C)	150
Ions (<i>m/z</i>)	DMP: 163 ^{Q,C} , 77 ^C and 92 ^C DEP: 149 ^{Q,C} , 177 ^C and 176 ^C 4-CDE: 204 ^{Q,C} , 206 ^C and 141 ^C 4-BDE: 248 ^{Q,C} and 141 ^C DBP: 149 ^{Q,C} , 150 ^C and 205 ^C DBP-d ₄ : 153 ^{Q,C} and 227 ^C BBP: 149 ^{Q,C} , 91 ^C and 206 ^C DEHA: 129 ^{Q,C} , 112 ^C and 147 ^C DEHP: 149 ^{Q,C} , 167 ^C and 279 ^C DNOP: 149 ^{Q,C} , and 279 ^C

^Q Quantification ions; ^C Confirmation ions.

Highlights

- A new GC-MS method was proposed for determining nine plasticizers in bee pollen.
- Sample treatment consists of a modified QuEChERS (acetonitrile and EMR-lipid).
- Good recovery percentages have been achieved for all the compounds (77%-104%).
- The LOQs were lower than the SMLs established by current legislation.
- Residues of five plasticizers were detected in some of the analyzed samples.

Supplementary Material

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A NEW ANALYTICAL METHOD FOR THE
DETERMINATION OF PLASTICIZERS IN BEE POLLEN**

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List of abbreviations employed in the Supplementary Material

ACN, acetonitrile; **BAGI**, Blue Applicability Grade Index; **4-BDE**, 4-bromodiphenyl ether; **C**, commercial sample; **4-CDE**, 4-chlorodiphenyl ether; **BBP**, butyl benzyl phthalate; **DBP**, dibutyl phthalate; **DEHA**, bis(2-ethylhexyl) adipate; **DEHP**, di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; **DEP**, diethyl phthalate; **DMP**, dimethyl phthalate; **DNOP**, di-*n*-octyl phthalate; **E**, experimental sample; **GC**, gas chromatography; **GCB**, graphitized carbon black; **HL**, high spiking level; **IT**, ion trap; **LOD**, limit of detection; **LOQ**, limit of quantification; **LL**, low spiking level; **ME**, matrix effect; **ML**, medium spiking level; **MS**, mass spectrometry; **MS/MS**, tandem mass spectrometry; **NS**, not specified; **OC**, overall content; **PAE**, phthalate esters; **PSA**, primary secondary amine; **QqQ**, triple quadrupole; **QuEChERS**, Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged & Safe; **R**, recovery; **%RSD**, relative standard deviation; **SE**, solvent extraction; **SM**, sample mass; **SPE**, solid phase extraction; **UVA-DLLME**, ultrasound-vortex-assisted dispersive liquid–liquid microextraction.

Table 1S.- Comparison of analytical methods for the determination of plasticizers in bee products and other food matrices.

Food matrix (SM)	Analytes	Sample treatment	Analytical method	ME	%R	LOD/LOQ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	BAGI index	Ref.
Honey (2.5 g)	6 PAEs	UVA-DLLME (toluene and NaCl)	GC-MS/MS (IT)	NS	88–99	2–6/ 5–11	65.0	[21]
Honey (2.5 g)	6 PAEs	UVA-DLLME (benzene and NaCl)	GC-MS/MS (IT)	NS	93–100	3–13/7–22	65.0	[22]
Honey (5.0 g) Royal jelly (1.0 g)	22 PAEs	SE (hexane-honey; hexane/acetone-royal jelly)	GC-MS	No	80–111	0.3–15/1–50	65.0	[23]
Honey (1.0 g)	4 PAEs	DLLME (ACN and chloroform)	GC-MS	Yes	> 82	0.6-2.0	75.0	[24]
Honey (5.0 g)	6 PAEs	SPE (Oasis HLB and methanol)	GC-MS	Yes	81–120	3–3200/ 12–13100 (mg L^{-1})	62.5	[25]
Honey (1.0 g)	6 PAEs, 1 adipate, 2 diphenyl ethers	Modified QuEChERS (ethyl acetate and Florisil)	GC-MS	Yes	77–118	0.1–3.1/ 0.1–10.3	60.0	[27]
Mussels (0.1 g)	6 PAEs	Modified QuEChERS (ACN and Florisil)	GC-MS	No	78–110	0.16–11.4/ 0.53–38.0	65.0	[42]
Capsanthin (0.5 g)	17 PAEs	Modified QuEChERS (ACN and Florisil)	GC-MS	Yes	83–118	200–500/ 600–1500	70.0	[43]
Edible oil (0.5 g)	15 PAEs	Modified QuEChERS (Methanol, GCB and PSA)	GC-MS/MS (QqQ)	Yes	70–115	0.01–8.00/ 0.04–26.68	62.5	[44]
Baby food (10.0 g)	14 PAEs, 1 adipate	Modified QuEChERS (ACN, PSA and MgSO_4)	GC-MS/MS (QqQ)	Yes	70–120	NS/0.03–1.11	60.0	[45]
Bee pollen (1.0 g)	6 PAEs, 1 adipate, 2 diphenyl ethers	Modified QuEChERS (ACN and EMR Lipid)	GC-MS	Yes	77–104	0.2–17.2/ 0.5–57.5	65.0	Present study

Table 2S.- Bee pollen samples analyzed in the present study.

Sample	Origin	Packaging	Palynological analysis
E1	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E2	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E3	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E4	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E5	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E6	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E7	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E8	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E9	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E10	Marchamalo (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
E11	Marchamalo (Spain)	Plastic	Cistus L.
E12	Marchamalo (Spain)	Plastic	Multifloral
E13	Marchamalo (Spain)	Plastic	Multifloral
E14	Marchamalo (Spain)	Plastic	Brassica t.
E15	Marchamalo (Spain)	Plastic	Multifloral
C1	Granada (Spain)	Plastic	Multifloral
C2	Valladolid (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
C3	Spain	Plastic	Multifloral
C4	Spain	Plastic	Multifloral
C5	Spain	Glass	Multifloral
C6	Spain	Glass	Chestnut
C7	Spain	Glass	Multifloral
C8	Galicia (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
C9	Galicia (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
C10	Castilla y León (Spain)	Glass	Multifloral
C11	Spain	Glass	Multifloral
C12	Spain	Glass	Multifloral
C13	Spain	Glass	Chestnut
C14	Spain	Glass	Multifloral
C15	Galicia (Spain)	Glass	Chestnut

Table 3S.- Evaluation of the extraction efficiency (recovery percentages, %R) and the matrix effect (ME) when evaluating different sorbents for the dispersive solid-phase extraction step with spiked blank bee pollen samples. Data obtained as described in **subsections 2.2, 3.1 and 3.3**. Results were obtained from three replicates that were injected in triplicate, and relative standard deviation (%RSD) were lower than 15% in all cases. Experiments: **T1:** no sorbent addition (0.25. mg L⁻¹); **T2:** EMR-Lipid (0.25 mg L⁻¹); **T3:** EMR-Lipid and C₁₈ (0.25 mg L⁻¹); **T4:** EMR-Lipid and Florisil (0.25 mg L⁻¹); **T5:** EMR-Lipid (0.5 mg L⁻¹); **T6:** EMR-Lipid and C₁₈ (0.5 mg L⁻¹).

Analyte	T1		T2		T3		T4		T5		T6	
	%R	%ME	%R	%ME	%R	%ME	%R	%ME	%R	%ME	%R	%ME
DMP	118	*19	87	+26	86	+20	124%	+29	84	+36	111%	+133
DEP	106	+153	82	+4	87	+24	132%	+25	79	-6	77%	+31
4-CDE	102	+106	81	-22	76	+7	119%	-27	85	-17	66%	+34
4-BDE	96	+40	78	-2	77	-17	118%	-21	96	+2	69%	+1
DBP	120	+406	88	-19	87	-46	133%	-46	85	-39	80%	-33
BBP	125	+284	88	+117	101	+180	128%	+117	91	+129	92%	+274
DEHP	123	+376	85	+53	76	+49	145%	+37	83	+45	65%	+48
DNOP	102	+374	97	+123	66	+123	135%	+30	95	+114	52%	+383

Table 4S.- Evaluation of the extraction efficiency (recovery percentages; %R) of the sample treatment and the matrix effect (mean values; %ME). Data obtained as described in Sections 2.2, 3.1 and 3.3. The results were obtained from three replicates that were injected in triplicate, and relative standard deviation (%RSD) were lower than 15% in all cases.

Spiking level Compound	LL		ML		HL	
	%R	%ME	%R	%ME	%R	%ME
DMP	92	+29	87	+33	84	+36
DEP	86	+12	85	+6	79	-6
4-CDE	83	-23	77	-27	85	-17
4-BDE	102	-12	94	-9	96	-7
DBP	88	-32	80	-35	85	-39
BBP	95	+138	88	+138	91	+129
DEHA	86	+111	78	+110	81	+105
DEHP	84	+58	87	+48	83	+45
DNOP	104	+140	99	+121	95	+114

LL, low level (LOQ, see Table 1); **ML**, medium level (0.4 mg kg⁻¹); **HL**, high level (2.0 mg kg⁻¹).

Table 5S.- Procedures employed for determining the validation parameters. Reprinted from Food Chemistry, 408, Adrián Fuente-Ballesteros, Patricia Brugnerotto, Ana C.O. Costa, María J. Nozal, Ana M. Ares, José Bernal, Determination of acaricides in honeys from different botanical origins by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, 135245, Copyright (2023), with permission from Elsevier.

Validation parameter	Experimental procedure
Selectivity	This was evaluated by comparing the chromatograms and mass spectra of standards in solvents, standard in matrix extracts and blank bee pollen (n = 6).
Limits of detection and quantification	The limits of detection (LODs) and quantification (LOQs) were determined by the injection of several blank sample measurement noise at the elution times for the studied plasticizers and comparing this response (mean values) with the signal (peak heights) of compounds at low concentration levels. The LODs and LOQs were estimated to be three and ten times the S/N ratio, respectively. In addition, it was checked that LOQs met the identification and method performance criteria for recovery (70%-120%) and precision (< 20%).
Matrix effect	To ascertain how the matrix influenced ionization for the studied plasticizers a comparison was made of the detector responses (analyte peak area/IS area) of standard in solvent and standard in matrix extracts (AF samples) spiked at three different concentrations (low, medium, and high spiking levels). It was calculated as follows: $\text{Matrix effect (in \%)} = \left(\left(\frac{R_{\text{matrix}}}{R_{\text{solvent}}} \right) - 1 \right) \times 100$ <p>R_{matrix}: detector response from standard in matrix extract. R_{solvent}: detector response from standard in solvent.</p>
Linearity/Working range	Calibration curves (n = 6) were constructed by plotting the signal on the y-axis (analyte peak area/IS area) against the analyte concentration on the x-axis. Linearity was evaluated by visual analysis of the plots, a calculation being made of the determination coefficients (R^2), and by our back calculation of the concentrations of the individual calibration standards.

Table 5S.- Continued.

Validation parameter	Experimental procedure
Precision	Precision, which was expressed as relative standard deviation (% RSD), experiments were performed concurrently by repeated sample analysis using BF samples, either on the same day (repeatability), or over three consecutive days (partial reproducibility).
Trueness	<p>It was evaluated by means of recovery experiments (as a measure of trueness), by comparing the results (analyte peak area/IS area) obtained from blank bee pollen samples spiked at three different concentrations (low, medium, and high levels), either prior to (BF samples) or following (AF samples) sample treatment. It was calculated as follows:</p> $Recovery (in \%) = \frac{R_{BF \text{ sample}}}{R_{AF \text{ sample}}} \times 100$ <p>$R_{BF \text{ sample}}$: detector response from BF sample. $R_{AF \text{ sample}}$: detector response from AF sample.</p>

Table 6S.- Summary of precision studies (%RSD values) for the determination of plasticizers in spiked blank bee pollen samples.

Compound	Repeatability			Partial reproducibility		
	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
DMP	7	9	10	5	7	9
DEP	11	8	8	9	13	10
4-CDE	12	10	9	6	10	7
4-BDE	7	8	11	7	7	9
DBP	8	6	10	10	12	8
BBP	9	12	10	7	9	7
DEHA	7	9	5	6	7	9
DEHP	9	12	10	14	10	12
DNOP	4	8	7	5	8	6

Low, LOQ (see Table 1); Medium, 0.400 mg kg⁻¹; High, 2.000 mg kg⁻¹

Table 7S.- Results (means of triplicate analyses and overall content (OC) expressed in mg kg⁻¹; %RSD < 15% in all cases) of the investigation of the studied plasticizers in bee pollen samples. The other compounds under study were below LOD in the samples. LODs and LOQs are summarized in **Table 1**.

Sample	DEP	DBP	BBP	DEHA	DEHP	OC
E1	0.038	0.070	0.060	0.063	<LOD	0.231
E2	<LOD	0.006	0.126	0.055	<LOD	0.187
E3	0.127	0.111	0.657	0.257	0.019	1.171
E4	<LOD	0.006	<LOQ	0.077	<LOD	0.083
E5	<LOD	0.005	0.059	0.056	<LOD	0.120
E6	0.012	0.015	0.165	0.080	<LOD	0.272
E7	0.023	0.021	0.065	0.129	<LOQ	0.233
E8	<LOD	0.007	<LOD	0.050	<LOD	0.057
E9	0.019	0.050	0.551	0.215	0.013	0.848
E10	0.260	0.103	2.414	0.344	0.031	3.152
E11	0.029	0.107	0.171	0.078	0.019	0.404
E12	0.135	0.092	0.265	0.115	0.084	0.691
E13	<LOD	0.031	0.210	0.105	0.065	0.411
E14	<LOD	0.085	0.342	0.118	0.072	0.617
E15	<LOD	0.035	0.105	0.058	0.020	0.218
C1	<LOD	0.010	<LOD	0.062	<LOD	0.072
C2	<LOD	0.016	<LOD	0.055	<LOD	0.071
C3	0.058	0.048	0.275	0.092	0.037	0.510
C4	<LOD	0.010	<LOD	0.057	<LOD	0.067
C5	<LOQ	0.010	0.012	0.065	<LOQ	0.087
C6	<LOQ	0.024	<LOD	0.050	<LOD	0.074
C7	<LOD	0.033	0.116	0.101	<LOD	0.250
C8	0.046	0.064	<LOD	0.101	0.142	0.187
C9	<LOD	0.009	<LOD	0.051	<LOD	0.060

Table 7S.- Continued.

Sample	DEP	DBP	BBP	DEHA	DEHP	OC
C10	0.054	<LOQ	0.249	0.098	<LOD	0.642
C11	<LOD	0.014	<LOD	0.075	<LOD	0.089
C12	<LOD	0.082	<LOD	0.062	0.175	0.319
C13	<LOD	0.015	<LOD	0.031	0.046	0.092
C14	<LOD	0.009	<LOD	0.060	<LOD	0.069
C15	<LOD	0.013	<LOD	0.043	<LOQ	0.056

Figure 1S.- Chemical structure of the plasticizers investigated in this article.

Figure 2S.- Analytical procedure work-up flow chart.

